

ISic3519

Epitaph of Aurelia Agoraste Hilaritas

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido , sep.75

Coordinates

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3564

Physical Description

A marble slab, which appears to have been intact in Orsi's day, but is now
missing upper left and right corners, with damage along
the top edge

Dimensions

Height 23.7 cm
Width 23.7 cm
Depth 1.7-2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 5: 16-18 mm

Text

1. [Αύ]ρηλί [α]
2. [Α]γοράστη
3. ψυχὴ ἀσύν
4. κριτος · Ἰλαρί τας · ἐβίωσε · ἔτη π'

Apparatus

Text based on I.Messina 10

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493848

EDCS 38200006

PHI 313636

Bibliography

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